

Thermodynamic Approach to Quantum Mechanics and the Question of Pressure

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Quantum mechanics and classical statistical mechanics/thermodynamics are both statistical theories, but have key differences. We argue that one such key difference is nonlocality in the quantum world i.e a wavelength proportional to $1/p$ and a probability of $\exp(ipx)$ associated with p versus locality in the classical case. Quantum nonlocality tends to lead to spatial densities with humps even for a particle with a fixed energy in an infinite potential box.

Recently it has been suggested in (1) that one may think of a quantum particle in a box with infinite walls in terms of thermodynamical properties e.g. pressure which is taken to be constant throughout the box. From this assumption, one finds that quantum entropy is $\ln[\text{Average}(n_x n_x + n_y n_y + n_z n_z)]$. For a single quantum state, this seems to imply that entropy is $\ln[n_x n_x + n_y n_y + n_z n_z]$ ((1a)).

In a previous note (2), we suggested that quantum entropy for a wavefunction (say an eigenstate) is $\int dx W^*(x)W(x) \ln[W^*W] + \int dp a^*(p)a(p) \ln[a^*(p)a(p)]$ ((1b)). We found this is independent of L for a particle in a box with infinite walls so that displacing the wall adiabatically should mean that $dS/dL = 0$ which it does as L cancels from ((1)).

We argue in this note that quantum pressure should be linked to the density humps for a $\sin(pave x)\sin(pave x)$ wavefunction even though $pave$ is constant at all x points. Thus it seems that one would not consider a constant pressure for $\sin(pave x)=\text{wavefunction}$. Furthermore ((1b)) does not yield the same entropy as ((1a)). It is noted in (1) that ((1a)) is an exact expression for entropy and that the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution entropy approximates it. In this note, we argue that a time reversal balanced scattering reaction leads to the Fermi-Dirac and Bose-Einstein distributions and these both lead to the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution under certain conditions. (The Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution may also be obtained from time reversal balanced scattering with looser restrictions.)

Quantum Mechanical Pressure

In a previous note (3) we argued that $V(x)$ instead of accelerating a particle from x to $x+dx$ is really an average of impulse hits (momentum transfers). Given that it is an average, it should consist of probabilities which yield a force proportional to various p (momenta) multiplied by probability if one takes $-d/dx$ i.e.

$$V(x)=\text{Sum over } k \text{ } V_k \exp(ikx) \text{ and } -dV/dx = \text{Sum over } k \text{ } -ik V_k \exp(ikx) \quad ((2))$$

Similarly a quantum particle represents a momentum impulse hit and is described by $\exp(ipx)$ i.e. it is nonlocal and has a wavelength proportional to $1/p$ where p is momentum. Thus a hit of momentum p occurs anywhere within the wavelength, but there are different probabilities for the particle to be a point x . $\exp(ipx)$ is two dimensional so the particle may be partly off along an axis perpendicular to x . For a bound state (say a particle in a box with infinite walls) $\exp(i pave x)$ and $\exp(-i pave x)$ superpose to create $2\cos(pave x)$ i.e. a varying density within the wavelength region. This seems to suggest different pressures within this region which seems to

match experimental measurements of the humps of spatial density. For a measurement to detect that a wavefunction's modulus squared has humps (e.g. an oscillator wavefunction etc) it must encounter higher pressure in one region and lower in another. Similarly for a two slit experiment, regions with light should have higher pressure than dark nodes as the photons create light as well as pressure.

This nonlocality is an important difference between quantum and classical mechanics and suggests that even though $K_{Eave}(x) = [-1/2m d/dx dW/dx] / W = K_{Eclasscal}(x)$ so that $v_{rms}(x)$ is classical, the presence of density $W*W$ suggests that matters are very different as there are density humps. Classically in a statistical gas, if there is higher density and hence higher pressure ($PV=nRT$ ideal gas law) at one x point versus another, a force must exist to counter this pressure difference. This is a local picture. In quantum mechanics both a force impulse piece and a particle represented by $\exp(ipx)$ have a fixed momentum p suggesting a fixed force, but a nonlocal wavelength region with varying pressure or probability. This allows for superposition to create an rms picture which matches classical physics in a bound state. Thus the ideas of thermodynamics, we argue, apply to rms values which is what are used in (1) to write a pressure even for a quantum eigenstate in a box with infinite potential walls i.e. (from (1))

$$\text{Pressure} = mvv / (3LLL) = \frac{2}{3} E_n / (LLL)$$

$$\text{Here } E_n = [\hbar^2 * 3.14^2 n^2 / L^2] [\hbar^2 * 3.14^2 n^2 / L^2] (1/2m) \quad ((3))$$

is an average value. The wavefunction $\sin(pave x)$ Normalization (which exists from 0 to L) and is 0 elsewhere is really a superposition of $\exp(ipx)$ terms which exist for all x and represent physical impulse hits. In other words, an rms value is really an approximation to the problem which allows a quantum state to appear as a classical pressure and energy. This might not be an issue if the two led to the same entropy expression, but it seems they do not.

Entropy from (1)

In (1) it is argued that PV^g where g is $cp/cv = 5/2$ is a constant for an adiabatic thermodynamic process. Using rms values for a quantum state (4) states that for a particle in a box with infinite walls:

$$\text{Pressure (state } n) = mvv / (3LLL) = \frac{2}{3} E_n / (LLL) \quad ((4))$$

This result applies to a single quantum state. In (1) it is stated that entropy is:

$$S = \text{entropy} = \ln[P V^{5/3}] \quad ((5))$$

$$\text{From ((4)) one may see that } S = \ln[\frac{2}{3} (n_x n_x + n_y n_y + n_z n_z) (2 * 3.14)^3] \quad ((6))$$

For a quantum gas with many particles in various states:

$(n_x n_x + n_y n_y + n_z n_z)$ is replaced by $\text{Average}(n_x n_x + n_y n_y + n_z n_z)$.

Furthermore in (1) it is argued that Maxwell-Boltzmann entropy approximates ((6)).

Shannon's Entropy for a Quantum State

In (2) we argued that Shannon's entropy $-\sum_n P(n) \ln(P(n))$ where $P(n)$ is probability of n is created using:

Probability = $W(x) a(p) \exp(-ipx)$ where $W(x)$ =wavefunction= $\sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx)$

which leads for a bound state with $W^*(x)=W(x)$ and $a^*(p)=a(p)$ to:

$$\text{Entropy} = \int dx W(x)W(x) \ln\{WW\} + \int dp a(p)a(p) \ln[a(p)a(p)] \quad ((7))$$

We showed in (2) that this entropy for a particle in a box does not depend on L . Thus if the box length were increased adiabatically the entropy should stay the same as it does if it is independent of L .

The problem we encounter is that the value of ((7)) does not seem to match that of ((6)). ((6)) is based on n values characterizing quantum average energy.

If one calculates:

$$S_x = \int dx W(x)W(x) \ln[WW] \quad \text{with } W = \sqrt{2/L} \sin(kx) \quad \text{with } x \text{ ranging from } 0 \text{ to } L$$

letting $y = kx$ where $k = n \cdot 2\pi \cdot \hbar / L$ leads to:

$$S_x = b_1 \ln(2/L) + \int (0, n \cdot 2\pi \cdot \hbar / L) \frac{2}{L} \sin(y)\sin(y) \ln[\sin(y)\sin(y)] dy \quad (1/n) b_2$$

Where b_1 and b_2 are constants. Thus $n \cdot 2\pi \cdot \hbar / L$ means one integrates n cycles and obtains n *value for 1 cycle which is then divided by $1/n$. Thus n does not appear in S_x . In fact in (5)

$$S_x = \ln(2L/e) \quad \text{where } e \text{ approx } 2.7$$

From (5), if one takes the limit $n \rightarrow \infty$ one obtains a value independent of n for S_p . For smaller values of p it seems that S_p is n dependent, but not in the simple manner of $\ln(nn)$.

From (5)

$$a(p) = L / (2\pi \hbar) \left[\frac{2\pi \hbar}{2\pi \hbar + pL} \text{sinc}\left[\frac{1}{2}(2\pi \hbar - pL)\right] \right] \quad ((8))$$

One term of $a(p)a(p) \ln[a(p)a(p)]$ is $a(p)a(p) \ln(nn)$ where $\int dp a(p)a(p) = 1$. According to ((6)), $\ln(nn)$ should be the full answer for S . S_x contains no n value so this term $a(p)a(p) \ln(nn)$ should give the full answer for entropy. This, however, does not seem to be the case

because (5) shows that in the limit of $n \rightarrow \infty$ $S_p = \ln(b/L)$ where b is a constant not containing n .

Thus ((7)) does not seem to yield the result of ((6)) which is $\ln(nn)$ for entropy. Given the unusual entropy for each quantum state n for a particle in a box with infinite potential walls, how does one calculate the overall entropy?

Overall Entropy of a particle in Box with Infinite Walls

In the previous section we have argued that $S_x + S_p$ does not depend on L . It seems that it does, however, depend on n as S_x is n independent, but S_p should contain n . Thus there is an entropy associated with different energy states based on n , but this seems to be ignored in usual calculations with each energy state being considered as a state on the same footing (except for energy) and counting being done in terms of the occupation of states.

We have argued in previous notes that one may use time reversal reaction balance for such a problem. For the Fermi-Dirac or Bose-Einstein scenarios one has for $e_1 + e_2 = e_3 + e_4$ where e_i is the energy of the i th level:

$$f(e_1)[1 -/+ f(e_2)] f(e_2)[1 -/+ f(e_4)] = f(e_3) [1 -/+ f(e_1)] f(e_4)[1 -/+ f(e_2)] \quad ((9))$$

The Fermi-Dirac and Bose-Einstein distributions yield the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution under certain conditions or it may be obtained using $e_1 + e_2 = e_3 + e_4$ and $f(e_1)f(e_2) = f(e_3)f(e_4)$. One may note that $f(e_i)$ represents the average number of particles in state e_i so that quantum rules for fermions and bosons are applied using average $f(e_i)$ values. One obtains expressions for entropy from these distributions with the Maxwell-Boltzmann one approximating ((6)).

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that even though classical gas and quantum mechanical bound systems are both based on statistical scenarios, the two are different in physical nature. Classical statistical mechanics deals with local values i.e. values defined at x such as velocity or momentum. To find an equivalent local value in a quantum system one must use an rms value e.g. p_{rms} i.e. $KE_{ave}(x) = [-1/2m d/dx dW/dx]/W = KE_{classical}(x)$. Momentum, however, is associated with nonlocality in terms of spatial probabilities i.e. $\exp(ipx)$. Each $\exp(ipx)$ delivers a p momentum hit, but probabilities differ within the wavelength region. This leads to spatial density profiles $W^*(x)W(x)$ ($W(x)$ =wavefunction) which have humps. We argue that these represent different pressure regions even though p_{ave} may be the same in a hump and trough region e.g. for the case of a particle in a box with infinite walls. Due to the nonlocality of the problem one cannot think of pressure balances in a classical manner. Simply using rms values without considering the density humps yields classical results, but that is not the full picture.

In (1) an rms pressure is applied to a quantum eigenstate for a particle in a box and the entropy is found to be $\ln(n_x n_x + n_y n_y + n_z n_z)$. In this note we argue that entropy for a particle in state n is $\int dx W W \ln(W W) + \int dp a(p) a(p) \ln[a(p) a(p)]$. We argue that this does

not match $\ln(n_x n_x + n_y n_y + n_z n_z)$. Furthermore we argue that a form similar to $\ln(n_x n_x + n_y n_y + n_z n_z)$ follows from the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution which appears under certain limits of Fermi-Dirac or Bose-Einstein distributions.

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